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Executive Summary

Training aimed at early career researchers (ECRs) (e.g. Master and PhD students, and postdoctoral researchers) is essential for them to develop important skills for success in graduate degrees and future professional careers. Among others, this can include training in a variety of subject-specific, communication, project management, and other transferable skills.

As part of WP7 of the APPLICATE project, the Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) in cooperation with APPLICATE developed and conducted comprehensive and targeted in-person and online training events and resources for ECRs (see Figure 1), addressing a variety of topics and skills:

- The **APECS-APPLICATE Online Seminar Series** (Fall 2017): all three seminars combined were attended by 46 ECRs and the recordings have been viewed 279 times
- A **training session** on 17 January 2018 during the APPLICATE General Assembly 2018 (Barcelona, Spain) attended by approximately 10 ECRs
- The **Polar Prediction School 2018** (Abisko, Sweden, 17 - 27 April 2018) attended by 29 ECRs
- A **training workshop** from 30 January to 1 February 2019 during the APPLICATE General Assembly 2019 (Reading, UK) attended by approximately 10 ECRs
- The **APECS-APPLICATE-YOPP Online Course 2019 "Advancing Predictive Capability of Northern Hemisphere Weather and Climate"** (September - December 2019) attended by 125 ECRs in total
- A collection of **Polar Prediction Resources** on the APECS website

Overall, WP7 training activities were successful and represent valuable resources and a legacy of the APPLICATE project. This report includes a summary of the activities, the wealth of lessons learned from them and the recommendations provided for organizers of similar activities.

Figure 1. Timeline of the APPLICATE WP7 Training activities with in-person (in red) and online training events (in yellow). Timeline created using a template provided by <https://online.officetimeline.com>.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background and objectives

The Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) is an international organisation for undergraduate and graduate students, postdoctoral researchers, early faculty members, early career professionals, educators and others with interests in the Polar and Alpine regions as well as the wider cryosphere. APECS with its project office at the UiT The University of Norway (UiT) in Tromsø, Norway, was responsible within the **APPLICATE WP 7 "User Engagement, Dissemination and Training"** for organizing training and outreach activities. A variety of in-person and online training events and resources have been developed and conducted throughout the duration of the APPLICATE project. The target group were early career researchers (Master students, PhD candidates and postdoctoral researchers) in climate sciences. Topics included training in subject-specific, communication, project management, and other transferable skills.

1.2. Organisation of this report

This report provides a chronological overview and evaluation of the training activities throughout the lifetime of APPLICATE, including

- Detailed descriptions of content, organisation and outcomes of each activity
- Description and analysis of the results of evaluation surveys for selected activities
- Summaries of what worked well, and the lessons learned

For the APECS-APPLICATE-YOPP Online Course, a detailed list of recommendations for further similar courses is included.

The annex lists lecturers, participants and organisers including their affiliation, as well as selected visual summaries of the evaluation surveys.

2. WP 7 Training Activities

2.1. Online seminar series

A [series of online seminars](#) was organized from **September 2017 to January 2018** to introduce the APPLICATE project along with its research focus and goals.

Seminar 1: Advanced Prediction in Polar Regions and Beyond

- **Date:** 29 September 2017
- **Speaker:** Thomas Jung (Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Center for Polar and Marine Research / University of Bremen, Germany)
- **Content:** In November 2016, a European consortium of scientists from different disciplines set out to advance our capability to predict the weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond in the framework of the EU-funded project called APPLICATE. In this presentation, I will describe the basic rationale behind this project and outline what is needed to make step changes in our ability to predict Arctic weather and climate prediction, and to increase our understanding of the impact of Arctic climate change in mid-latitudes. In this context I will touch on the following topics: model evaluation, model development, teleconnections, observing system design, education and stakeholder engagement. To find out more about the APPLICATE project go to: <https://applycate.eu/>
- **Link of Recording:** <https://vimeo.com/237285327>

Seminar 2: Improving Weather and Climate Models

- **Date:** 29 November 2017
- **Speaker:** Matthieu Chevallier (MétéoFrance, Toulouse, France)
- **Content:** Weather and climate models have typically been developed for mid-latitude regions, but different processes are relevant for the Polar regions. Prediction in the Arctic and beyond using global models can be improved through a better representation of processes at the atmosphere-sea ice-ocean interface, including small-scale processes, and through a revisit of the atmosphere-ocean coupling strategy in coupled models. This seminar will focus on ‘Enhanced weather and climate models’, one of five science work packages of the EU-funded APPLICATE project, which brings together a European consortium of scientists from different disciplines to advance our capability to predict the weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond. To find out more about the APPLICATE project go to: <https://applycate.eu/>
- **Link of Recording:** <https://vimeo.com/245332535>

Seminar 3: Atmospheric-Oceanic linkages

- **Date:** 9 January 2018
- **Speaker:** Doug Smith (MetOffice, United Kingdom)
- **Content:** How does the Arctic influence mid-latitude weather and climate? What physical mechanisms play a role and how can we better model these processes? How does sea-ice loss affect the atmosphere and oceans in remote regions? Doug Smith, of the UK MetOffice, will discuss some of the science around these questions and how coordinated multi-model experiments can help to answer them. This seminar is the third in a series part of the EU-funded APPLICATE project. The APPLICATE project brings together a European consortium of scientists from different disciplines to advance our capability to predict the weather and climate in the Arctic and beyond. To find out more about the project go to: www.applycate.eu/.
- **Link of Recording:** <https://vimeo.com/250420364>

The seminars were advertised via APECS, APPLICATE as well as other list servers such as Cryolist or ArcticInfo, and were free to attend by everyone interested. They were recorded and uploaded to the APECS Vimeo account where they can be watched and downloaded by everyone.

Altogether, the three online seminars had **92 registrations, 46 attendees** and the recordings have been viewed **279 times (until August 2020)** (see Table 1 for more detailed information).

The number for registrations, attendees as well as views of the recordings show, that while the number of those attending the events might have been relatively low, more people were viewing the recordings afterwards using them as a learning and training resources.

Title	# Registrations	# Attendees	# views of recording
Advanced Prediction in Polar Regions and beyond	42	23	138
Improving Weather and Climate Models	33	14	66
Atmospheric-oceanic linkages	17	9	77
Totals	92	46	281

Table 1. Registration and attendee numbers derived from Zoom. Numbers for views of the recording based on Vimeo as of 25 September 2020.

2.2. ECR session at the APPLICATE General Assembly 2018

During the **APPLICATE General Assembly 2018** (15-17 January 2018 in Barcelona, Spain), a one-hour **training session on EU funding opportunities available to early career researchers** (ECRs) was held on 17 January. The session was attended by ca. **10 ECRs** from the APPLICATE project. Presentations were given by

- **Nancy Lange** (AWI Department of Research Support) and
- **Isadora Christel** (Barcelona Supercomputing Center)

providing some useful advice, followed by a general discussion with all participants. Many of the ECRs were among others unfamiliar with some of the terminology used in EU projects, such as “deliverables”, “stakeholders”, “user groups”, “white papers” and so the explanations provided by the speakers were helpful to the attendees.

Lessons learned

The main criticism to the organizers was regarding the **timing of the session in parallel with the APPLICATE user group session**, which some would have found useful to attend.

Recommendations for the future

Recommendations for the future included **organizing a session where the ECRs can present their projects particularly to the user group**. Not only this would have provided an excellent opportunity for the ECRs to learn how to communicate their results in a way understandable to a broader audience, but it also would have been a chance for them to have more interactions and get feedback from the users.

2.3. Polar Prediction School 2018

2.3.1. Overview

The APPLICATE project, in cooperation with the World Meteorological Organization’s Polar Prediction Project (PPP) in occasion of the [Year of Polar Prediction \(YOPP\)](#), the [APECS](#) and other partners organized the [Polar Prediction School 2018](#) on weather and climate prediction in the polar regions from **17 – 27 April 2018 at Abisko Scientific Research Station in Abisko, Sweden**. The location for the course at the Abisko Scientific Research Station in Sweden, was ideal as it provided instructional facilities that are conveniently located in an environment well suited to Arctic observations.

The school brought together **29 early career researchers** from **nine different countries** and various career stages, from early PhD through to post-docs, as well as **13 instructors from six countries** (see Figure 2 and Appendix 5.1.).

In preparation for the school, the organizers collected and shared **practical information** about Abisko, travel, the school, accommodation in shared rooms and free-time activities with all participants and lecturers before the start of the school.

The **program** for the school was designed to provide a comprehensive overview of the main aspects related to polar weather and climate prediction. It included a combination of polar weather and climate theory lectures with practical exercises on modelling and field meteorology techniques as well as training sessions on transferable skills (see Figure 3 for the course schedule). The motivation for combining these topics was to provide participants with a complete overview of the components required to understand and predict polar weather, as they all form crucial pillars in training future experts in this field.

Figure 4. *Students of the Polar Prediction School 2018 set up a micrometeorological mast on Sweden's frozen Lake Torneträsk. Instruments on the mast provided data that the students used to study daily variations in the lower atmosphere and atmospheric turbulence and to evaluate atmospheric models. Photo credit: Fiona Tummon*

Radiosondes were launched every day and the soundings were uploaded to the Global Telecommunication System, which is used in operational forecasts. In addition, a mini intense observational period was held on one day where radiosondes were launched every six hours. This was to study the diurnal cycle of the polar boundary layer at the site, even though the weather conditions at the time were not ideally suited to this.

Daily weather briefings were made by the students each evening. They were asked to provide an overview of the day's weather, to compare the previous day's forecast with the observed radiosounding they made, and to analyze forecasts for the coming days using global and regional products. The daily weather briefings were an opportunity for the students to learn to interpret weather

forecasts in complex polar mountain environments, (such as where Abisko is located) and to better understand how today's models perform in such regions. Furthermore, they led to interesting discussions about modelling skills and uncertainty in polar regions.

Transferable skills training was provided through a dedicated science communication program, which included six evening sessions and an afternoon of final presentations. Topics covered included how to distil information, tailoring messages for specific audiences, using social media and slide design.

An **international and interdisciplinary** course such as the Polar Prediction School, bringing together a wide range of early career researchers and lecturers, helps build and maintain the community needed to address multi-disciplinary issues in polar prediction. Overall, the school was a great success and we recommend this model being used for any future field schools for early career researchers.

Acknowledgement: The Polar Prediction School 2018 was organized as part of the EU Horizon 2020-funded [APPLICATE](#) project, in cooperation with the World Meteorological Organization's [Polar Prediction Project](#) (PPP) in occasion of the [Year of Polar Prediction](#) (YOPP). It was also generously supported by the [World Climate Research Programme's](#) (WCRP) [Climate and Cryosphere](#) project (CliC), the [International Arctic Science Committee](#) (IASC), and the [Scientific Committee for Antarctic Research](#) (SCAR).

2.3.2. Course Survey

To evaluate the content, structure and organization of the Polar Prediction School 2018 and learn what to improve for future similar training activities, all participants were asked to participate in a [course evaluation survey](#). The survey results represent the opinions of **27 out of 29 course participants** (see Appendix 5.2 for further details).

a) Overall impression

The overall impression of the course was very positive. It had a relevant course curriculum that met the expectations of the participants (78%) and that covered an appropriate range of topics (74%). The participants were satisfied with what they learned during the school (85%), found the school useful for their career (96%) and everybody would recommend a similar future school to fellow early career scientists.

b) Content and teaching methods

Overall, the content of the school was much appreciated with a balanced mix of lectures, practical exercises, fieldwork and transferable skills sessions. The variety of different angles increased understanding for the broad range of topics.

The participants appreciated the excellent content of the **lectures** (78%), which were clear and interesting (81%) with enough time allocated to them. In general, all lecturers were perceived as very good communicators and giving engaging talks.

The value of the **practical exercises** was much appreciated. Combining these teaching methods with daily fieldwork on the frozen lake and radiosonde launches clearly added value to the course (93%) and made them the highlight of the course. The students particularly valued the opportunity to collect real-time observations in the Arctic, and to discuss and analyze them on site. Including observations and data assimilation exercises in the school was especially useful for PhD candidates who mainly work on theoretical models as it provided them with a better understanding for uncertainties and limitations when using observational data and reanalysis products.

The **transferable skills sessions on science communication** and making FrostBytes were evaluated as mostly useful (60%).

Overall, the international and interdisciplinary school provided a much-appreciated opportunity to network with other early career researchers and senior scientists. The informal atmosphere between a “great group of people” contributed to valuable discussions at a beautiful location.

What was the best part of the training school?

- *“The atmosphere between all people involved. Everyone was enjoying themselves and getting on brilliantly, a testament to the combination of an exciting location, interesting lectures and wonderful staff.” (Course participant)*
- *“Being able to meet students from across a range of disciplines was great and meant different people could share their expertise.” (Course participant)*

Recommendations for content improvements

Lectures:

- **Improve the logical order** of some lecture topics (*Note from the organizers: while a logical order of the lectures was initially attempted by the organizers during the school planning process, this had to be overthrown to accommodate availability of some of the lecturers due to their other professional or private commitments*).
- Focus on **selecting more senior scientists** as lecturers with deeper background knowledge of some topics.
- **Thematic improvements** to better cover the topics of sea ice, polar precipitation and predictability.

Practical Exercises

- Allocate even more time for the practical exercises to allow unfolding their full potential.
- Weather briefings should have a more defined time slot to prevent them from extending too much in the evenings.

Transferable skills / science communication sessions:

- **Better timing** to avoid organizing these sessions in the evenings: a longer and more central time in the schedule would better acknowledge the value of the science communication sessions and create an easier situation for the lecturer. It would make the sessions feel less rushed and participants would have more energy to be actively involved.
- **Better guidance** for making the FrostBytes by the instructor, as it was only sparsely provided: Among others, guidance should have been provided before the participants arrived in Abisko, so that they would have had more time to learn about the FrostBytes and find creative ideas for their own contribution.
- **focus on presentation training** as this is what most participants will need for conferences etc.

Additional Sessions Suggested:

As an **added session during the school**, the survey suggested an **informal poster session** at the beginning where all **school participants can present their research projects and focus**. This would help discussions and networking during the school and also would give the participants an opportunity to contribute to the program.

c) Practical organizational / logistical aspects

The feedback survey revealed that students **learned about the school** in 2 ways:

- Via advertisement through the APECS newsletter, other Arctic research community mailing lists (such as Cryolist and ArcticInfo), and social media,
- Others had been speaking to either colleagues and friends who attended a similar course in the past and highly recommended it, or to supervisors and colleagues who forwarded the information.

In the feedback survey, it was mentioned that information on the **expected background level** of the participants is helpful for the applicants to the school to gauge whether the program fits their level of expertise and knowledge.

The students appreciated **Abisko as the perfect location for a field school about Arctic topics (96% positive)**, as well as the highly satisfactory catering from Abisko Mountain Lodge and accommodation at the Abisko Scientific Research Station (74%).

Recommendations for logistical improvements

Feedback and suggestions for improvement was provided on several logistical aspects:

- For several practical modelling exercises, participants needed special software on their computers. Time for installing this software was allocated after arrival in Abisko but was hampered by the poor internet connection on site. To ensure that all computers of participants have the necessary software and are ready to be used from the first day, survey participants suggested to **collect and provide all software requirements and downloading packages (including the latest updates) a few days before the school** so that the participants have time to prepare their computers while having access to a reliable internet connection before travelling.
- **name tags and a printed program** would have been appreciated (*Note from the organizers: the organizers deliberately chose to not provide this to reduce use of printed materials*)
- While the **length** of the school (10 days), was reported by 78% of the participants as an appropriate length, some participants thought it was too long due to the amount of information provided.
- The **daily schedule** was perceived as being too busy with too long days (until 21:30 in the evening). This was partly caused by the 6 hourly intervals of the radiosonde launches. The students said it was more difficult to follow lectures in the late afternoon while afternoon fieldwork was less tough. Avoiding lengthy evening sessions at least on some days would also have helped to keep some of the days shorter. Another suggestion was to shorten the 2-hour

lunch break and rather lengthen the pre-dinner break. This would have given people a better chance for pre-dinner exercise.

- The participants recommended having **one day** (or at least an entire afternoon) **off** in the middle of the school. They would have also appreciated having more free time in the evenings (after dinner) for more exercising, exploring the area, discussions, socializing and private time.

To ensure a positive outcome, clear guidelines about expectations of the report and how to give the feedback were provided. Since the peer review was carried out in a larger group, the risk of inappropriate feedback from a single person was greatly reduced. The peer review went smoothly with all groups providing their input on time, written in a critical but positive tone, in a well-structured order and with constructive content. All groups considerably improved their case study after the peer review round.

2.3.3. Outcomes

The course organizers and lecturers published a **meeting report** about the school in the journal EOS:

Tummon, F., J. Day, and G. Svensson (2018), Training early-career polar weather and climate researchers, Eos, 99, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018EO103475>. Published on 08 August 2018.

The school participants also produced **brief informative videos ('FrostBytes')** about their research projects. They worked on them during the school and presented and recorded them on the final afternoon. The collection of 28 videos is available on the [APPLICATE website](#) and the [APECS Vimeo account](#).

What worked well

- The **mix of lectures and practical aspects** was appreciated
- The **location** was ideal
- The **atmosphere** during the course **facilitated good networking** among the students
- A **final evaluation** of the course using a survey **revealed useful details**

Lessons learned

- **Make a less busy schedule** with more time off for socializing, relaxing, sports and networking during a 10-day event
- **Distribute necessary software/download links in advance** of a course being held at a remote location to take advantage of better internet connections pre-arrival
- **Locate transferable skills sessions more central** in the course schedule
- Provide information on expected knowledge and experience during the application phase of the course to **give better orientation for the target group**

2.4. ECR Workshop at APPLICATE General Assembly 2019

The workshop took place directly after the [APPLICATE General Assembly 2019](#) at the [European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts \(ECMWF\)](#) in Reading, UK, from **30 January to 1 February 2019**. It was arranged for early career researchers from ECMWF and other APPLICATE partners to train transferable skills, to build expertise in Arctic weather and climate prediction, and to help building and maintaining a community of Arctic experts.

Figure 5. APPLICATE and ECMWF early career scientists gathered at ECMWF in Reading, UK. Photo credit: ECMWF.

The workshop was designed to help the early career researchers to get in touch with colleagues across the different APPLICATE work packages and ECMWF early career scientists to develop their professional network, and to practice presentation skills. Senior APPLICATE and ECMWF researchers gave interactive presentations and helped enhance transferable skill development (see Table 2). The sessions covered improving scientific writing, an introduction to project management, achieving co-production and stakeholder engagement, the relevance of computing for advancing science, challenges for weather forecasts in the Arctic, as well as an introduction to the Copernicus Climate Change Services and the Climate Data Store. The diverse research topics of the students and the mix of themes raised awareness of how to communicate with researchers from different backgrounds and stakeholders.

Wednesday 30 January 2019		
14:00-15:30	Research presentations I	Students
15:30-16:30	Coffee break	
16:30-18:00	Research presentations II	Students
From 18:00	Social evening at the Reading climbing centre	
Thursday 31 January 2019		
9:00-9:30	How to enjoy writing your next paper?	François Massonnet (Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium)
10:00-10:30	Why computing may be more relevant for advancing science than you think	Peter Bauer (ECMWF, UK)
11:00-12:00	Coffee break	

12:00-12:30	Make sense of the mess: How to keep your research project on track	Luisa Cristini (APPLICATE Project Coordinator, AWI, Germany)
13:00-14:00	Lunch	
14:00-18:00	Moving the iceberg: achieving co-production in climate services	Dragana Bojovic, Marta Terrado (Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Spain)
From 18:00	Social dinner	
Friday 1 February 2019		
9:00-10:00	Challenges related to improving weather predictions in the Arctic	Irina Sandu (ECMWF, UK)
10:00-10:30	Coffee break	
10:30-12:00	The Copernicus Climate Change Service in action	Jean-Noel Thepault, Cedric Bergeron (ECMWF, UK)
12:00-13:00	Conclusions/Feedback	
13:00-14:00	Lunch	
14:00	Departure from venue	

Table 2. The agenda of the Early Career Researcher Event in Reading in January 2019.

What worked well

- The **balance between academic, practical and social aspects** was much appreciated.
- **Having a social event early during the meeting** was a good idea as it gives everyone an opportunity to catch up and dive deeper into conversations about certain scientific questions.
- The session on stakeholder engagement **challenged the participants** as they were **invited to leave their comfort zones** and engage in an interactive role play.

Lessons learned

- One point of criticism was that the research presentations of the early career researchers were long and unfortunately few senior researchers were present. A better way to accommodate this could be a **general poster session early in the meeting with all APPLICATE scientists present** and that runs parallel with or leads over to an ice breaker.
- The organizers noticed rather low participation by early career researchers in the session, partially due to it being held after the APPLICATE Assembly had finished and not all ECRs were able to stay an extra day. Their **advisors should be made more aware of the benefits and values of transferable skills training and encourage and fund their students to attend these extra sessions.**

2.5. APECS-APPLICATE-YOPP Online Course on "Advancing Predictive Capability of Northern Hemisphere Weather and Climate"

2.5.1. Overview

Throughout fall 2019, APECS, the APPLICATE project and the [Year of Polar Prediction \(YOPP\)](#) were running an open [online course on "Advancing Predictive Capability of Northern Hemisphere Weather and Climate"](#).

The course provided an overview of the state-of-the-art knowledge of Northern high-latitude weather and climate predictions. It was designed for early career researchers (e.g., Master and PhD students, Postdocs) with a specific interest in Arctic weather and climate prediction and modelling. Table 3 summarizes the course schedule.

The course included 11 online seminars taught by 12 international experts from 7 countries once a week from **19 September to 5 December 2019**. The agenda of the course including web links to the recorded sessions can be viewed on the [course website](#) and in Table 3.

To receive a course certificate, the course participants were required to actively attend ten of the **12 seminars**, as well as work on and present a **practical group task** (case study, see more information below). An example of the course certificate is provided in Appendix 5.5.

Date	Title	Presenter	Duration (min)
Block 1: Introduction			
19 Sept	Course introduction: Advancing Predictive Capability of Northern Hemisphere Weather and Climate	Thomas Jung (Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar & Marine Research, Germany)	90
26 Sept	Stakeholder engagement and examples of APPLICATE case studies	Marta Terrado & Dragana Bojovic (Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Spain)	70
03 Oct	Boundary layer, clouds and air mass transformation	Gunilla Svensson (Stockholm University, Sweden)	70
Block 2 - Data and modelling			
17 Oct	Observing system design in the Arctic	Taneil Uttal (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, United States)	80
24 Oct	The use of Arctic observations in Numerical Weather Prediction	Heather Lawrence (European Center For Medium Range Weather Forecasts, UK)	50
31 Oct	Seasonal to decadal prediction: recent progress & signal-to-noise paradox	Doug Smith (MetOffice, United Kingdom)	80
07 Nov	Arctic weather phenomena and extremes	Thomas Spengler (University of Bergen, Norway)	90
Block 3 - Arctic			
14 Nov	Polar ocean forecasting	Arlan Dirkson (Université du Québec à Montréal, Canada)	90
21 Nov	Challenges and priorities for improved prediction and climate monitoring of the Arctic	Irina Sandu (European Center For Medium Range Weather Forecasts, UK)	70
28 Nov	Evaluating models	Barbara Casati (Environmental and Climate Change Canada)	90
04 Dec	Case study presentation seminar	Course participants	90

05 Dec	APPLICATE and the Year Of Polar Prediction (YOPP)	Jonathan Day (European Center For Medium Range Weather Forecasts, UK)	60
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Table 3. Schedule of the [online course on "Advancing Predictive Capability of Northern Hemisphere Weather and Climate" in fall 2019.](#)

a) Online Seminars

Each **online lecture** was divided into a general introduction (to accommodate students with less specific scientific background) followed by a more specific part, a Mentimeter Quiz to make sure relevant concepts were understood or needed to be revised, and time for Q&A at the end. In preparation for each seminar, the lecturers provided the top 3-5 scientific papers on their topic and thus helped build a literature collection that was supporting the course.

Figure 6. The showcase of the 12 sessions on the APECS Vimeo platform.

In total, **125 participants** followed several or all seminars and challenged the lecturers with detailed questions. An average attendance number per session was at 39. The course participants were Master, PhD students and Postdocs from Europe, North and South America, Africa and Asia.

“The course has given opportunities to gain new knowledge on highly debated research topics from leading experts and the involvement of various stakeholders and policy makers.”

(Course participant)

b) Practical Course Tasks

Participants were required to work in groups on an **APPLICATE Case Study** and present it at the end of the course. The APPLICATE project is **investigating extreme weather events** and its impact on society and economy in selected [case studies](#). These case studies are a particularity of APPLICATE and **focus on how advanced weather and climate prediction**

knowledge can be applied to solve a practical problem and to make a difference in everyday life of society.

APPLICATE researchers introduced the course participants to why and how research can be communicated to different stakeholders through examples of these APPLICATE case studies. Learning about the format of case studies and how they are developed outlined the attractive and appreciated opportunity for the students to work as a group on their own case study. This practical task gave room for the student's own interests and creativity next to learning about this format of science communication.

The topic areas for the course case studies offered to the participants to work on were renewable energy, health in the Arctic, safety/insurance issues in the Arctic, biodiversity and conservation, and local infrastructure.

The **plan of action for the case studies** included the following milestones:

1. Getting to know the group and finding a group leader,
2. Perform literature review and define the scope of the case study,
3. Developing the case study,
4. First draft,
5. Peer review,
6. Improving the project,
7. Final presentation.

Once the drafts of the case studies were produced, the groups performed a peer-review of a case study from another group to practice commenting and reviewing skills as these are rarely taught in a course. At the end of the course, the participants presented their case study in an online seminar and received comments from them from the course lecturers.

2.5.2. Course survey

To evaluate the content, structure and organisation of the online course and learn what to improve for future similar events, all participants were asked to provide feedback in an evaluation survey. The survey results represent the opinions of 40 course participants and Appendix 5.4 presents selected survey results.

a) Overall Impression

The overall impression of the course was very positive. It had a relevant course curriculum that met the expectations of the participants (92%) through making cutting-edge scientific information accessible. The participants gained a deeper insight in Polar weather and climate predictions (97%) and much appreciated the combination of lectures and practical work (82%).

The participants considered as strength and weaknesses of the course:

Strength

- Structure with **focused lectures that were combined with a practical task**
- **Internationality and interactivity** while being cost-efficient
- **Free and open access** to everyone interested in the course topic, regardless of their location and background, which helped build the cross-disciplinary character of the course. Bringing together a large diversity of experts and people with similar interests yet different perspectives fosters a learning environment where students gain insight into a topic from a variety of aspects.

Weakness

- **Communication and collaboration across time zones** was challenging. The students found their own way of communication, e.g. through WhatsApp in addition to email, and realized the importance of checking email regularly for course updates.
- In some groups, only a few people contributed to the project or **unequal commitment** of the group members **occurred**. Students dropping out of a course cannot be completely avoided particularly in an online activity.

b) Course content and learning outcome

The students valued the schedule with a wide range of relevant topics and the cutting-edge level of scientific information. The lectures were well structured and focused, were given by leading experts in their respective fields of research and sufficient time for Q&A discussion time at the end of each session provided opportunities to ask questions directly.

A highlight of the course was having **access to a panel of highly qualified experts** that are willing to share their knowledge and experience with the younger generation. This appeared to be excellent motivation to attend the course while pursuing a career in Arctic science.

Quiz questions with Mentimeter were used to check in with the participants if they have learned and understood main concepts and important details, or if any of them need to be revisited and explained better before moving on.

In general, sufficient time was allocated to the curriculum subjects (87%). The majority of the students spent 2-3 hours (45%) or 3-4 hours (30%) per week with course tasks (attending online seminars, reading, group work) while only few spent either more (7%: 4-6h) or less time (17%: 1-2h).

The course helped develop or improve a wide range of the participant's skills and abilities that reach far beyond conveying scientific information:

- Better insights of linkages between research goals and societal concerns (82%)
- Deeper understanding of the subject (77.5%)
- Working in an international team and across time zones (75%)
- Communicating and presenting in a diverse group of people (55%)
- Using online tools (40%) such as Zoom

The point on “better insights of linkages between research goals and societal concerns” highlights the value of the case studies for the course as they allowed the students to tackle real world problems.

c) Case studies and group work

The case studies provided an opportunity to gain greater insight into a certain topic and area together with a comprehensive group of young, enthusiastic scientists. The students enjoyed the experience of working with people from all over the globe and learning through the different perspectives of the group members. **Redefining an academic topic with a practical background made the science tangible**, and the students developed their project and supported each other while working on a **shared product**. The case studies clearly contributed to a deeper understanding of the linkages between society and science and thus became another **highlight of the course**.

Discussions within the groups ranged not only about the topic and how to shape the case study, but also about finding suitable ways and times to communicate, how to cooperate, build a consensus and make decisions in a team with members who have different backgrounds, come from different cultures and have with different viewpoints. Thus, the **group work was appreciated as a new vector to improve collaboration and leadership skills**.

Challenges of the group task

Challenges for the group task lay in getting started, establishing efficient communication within the group, reaching an agreement about the scope of the case study, and varying commitment of single group members:

- **Almost all groups would have appreciated better and more individual guidance in the beginning on how to coordinate the group and get started.** After communications and work rhythms were established, the groups picked up pace, responded timely to the regular check-ins and managed their projects well. Every group was recommended to choose a group leader, and some did so while others did not.
- **Managing communication across time zones was challenging initially.** Group email lists were provided late which made it difficult for the group members to get in touch right away and find their preferred ways of communication.
- **Reaching an agreement about the scope of the case study was challenging for some groups.** The course organisers chose to offer five generally formulated topic areas for the case studies to allow the groups to define the particular focus of their project themselves. This degree of freedom was deliberately chosen to invite a wide range of ideas.

d) Organisation

Overall, the course organisers provided suitable guidance and feedback (90%) for a smoothly-organised course and well-hosted online seminars. However, **more specific guidance for the group tasks** would have been appreciated.

The participants appreciated the regularity of the course and efficiently and timely communicated updates on changes to the schedule or varying seminar times. The times moved occasionally by 1-2 hours due to time zone issues and other professional or private commitments of the lecturers. Very short feedback surveys after each seminar were sent out to the participants and allowed various smaller improvements on the go.

Considering both the limitations and possibilities of the subject matter and the course, all participants were very satisfied with the overall effectiveness of the course. They particularly enjoyed the international experience that establishes and improves networks. The inclusive character of the course was appreciated as it encouraged students regardless of their background to get engaged in the course with all subject-related questions being welcome.

“Working with people from around the world that had varying insights due to where they studied or grew up. It was a melting pot of culture and knowledge.” (Course participant)

2.5.3. Outcomes

a) Student case studies

Six student groups were working on developing their case study across time zones and country borders. The topics of the case studies were:

- Predicting the 2018 Heatwave and Forest Fires in Sweden;
- Future hazard risks from Greenland ice sheet mass loss: Potential consequences for mid-latitudes with a focus on the possibility of a tsunami occurrence in Scotland;
- The 2012 Record Low Sea Ice Minimum and its Effect on Arctic Biodiversity;
- Hydropower in Iceland and its sensitivity to climate anomalies;
- Influence of ENSO on Arctic Climate;
- Flushed away: Addressing the types and hazards of flash floods in the Arctic.

The work on the case studies was valued by the participants as they enjoyed working with a comprehensive group of young, enthusiastic scientists from across the globe.

Challenges such as kicking off the group project, communication across time zones and different research backgrounds were confidently overcome by the student groups with the support of the course organisers and APPLICATE scientists. The participants' efforts resulted in the case studies being successfully completed and presented in a [dedicated online seminar](#) at the end of the course. The **six [case studies of the participants](#)** are available on the course website.

Participants who completed their case study, and attended the course lectures, received a course certificate (see Appendix 5.5.). This may be helpful to convert the course into ECTS points at their local university and include it in their degree program.

b) Online seminar collection

Each session was recorded and made available online via the [APECS Vimeo channel](#) shortly after the live session. Offering such an online course was an opportunity for APECS, the APPLICATE and YOPP projects and researchers to share their work and inspire the next generation of Arctic climate and weather experts from around the globe. Weblinks that were collected during the course - either provided by the lecturers or students - were included in the collection of Polar Prediction Resources (see section 7 in this document). The recordings and the collection of Polar Prediction Resources are forming a comprehensive and valuable resource and legacy of the APPLICATE and YOPP projects.

2.5.4. Recommendations for future online courses

Overall, there is a strong interest by early career researchers in online courses such as the APECS-APPLICATE-YOPP Online Course 2019. In our survey, 37 out of 40 participants would definitely recommend a similar future course to fellow early career scientists (an additional 3 responded with "maybe") as it helps progressing in this field of research.

To help future organizers and attendees of online courses, we have collected a number of recommendations and lessons learned that could be considered for future courses:

2.5.4.1. Recommendations for course participants

The feedback survey among the course participants revealed key advice to participants of future similar courses.

- **Set aside enough time** to attend all sessions and dedicate enough time for the project work. Do not underestimate the time effort required for a practical task such as the case study.
- **Read the provided literature** and **prepare questions** prior to the seminars. Getting in direct discussion with leading experts is a unique opportunity and being prepared helps making the most of this.
- **Check emails** regularly for updates, and
- **Place reminders** for the seminar dates and times in your personal calendar
- **Start early** with course projects
- Make **regular group communication** a priority
- **Use social media** (or other preferred means) to connect
- **Do not be afraid to take initiative**, participate and contribute even if one is new to the topic

2.5.4.2. Recommendations for organizers

What worked well

- **Online lectures** are not necessarily a one-way conveyor belt of learning but **can facilitate a dialogue** in a valuable way
- **Group work** can be **successful in a digital learning environment**
- The opportunity of receiving a **course certificate** was much appreciated by the participants

Lessons learned

- Especially for group work among students, **time zone differences** make equal participation more challenging
- In order to start and guide the group work better, **close guidance and regular check-ins** with separate meetings for each group (instead of email conversations) are recommended

Aside from these general recommendations, the organizers of the APECS-APPLICATE-YOPP Online Course 2019 have collected specific recommendations for logistics of organizing a similar course as well as the course content and its structuring:

Logistics:

Before the course

- **Lecturers:** Contact the lecturers about 6 months in advance as many will be travelling, in the field, on holiday, on leave, busy etc. Their schedules fill up quickly. When asking about specific times, use their local times as some get confused with GMT easily and do not convert to their local time zone. WorldTimeBuddy (<https://www.worldtimebuddy.com/>) is one of many time zone conversion options.
- **FAQ** on the course website are helpful.
- **Plan in extra time between closing the registration and the start of the course:** Reserve at least 1-2 weeks prior to the course start for last minute organizing (e.g. last-minute changes in participation level, setting up groups if you involve group work in the course etc.) and to answer questions from course participants.
- Zoom is an online platform that worked well for our course and is stable and works well. Ensure you book sessions with extra time around (for questions for presenters, to accommodate the schedules of the lecturer, if you are using a specific Zoom licence of an organization, check if there are other events that need the license afterwards and if necessary build in a time buffer for your seminar into the booking).

During the course

- **Send regular information** with e.g. change date, time/topic of the lecture, Zoom link. It is a lot more efficient to get the important info out regularly.
- Inform all participants early in case there are changes in the schedule (lecturers may travel and try to switch dates).
- **Include important links at the end of each course-related message** (such as course material/literature, course website/agenda, time zone converter).
- Keep records about student participation and contribution with regard to the course certificate
- Have a **Zoom test session** with every lecturer a few days prior to the seminar to test audio/sound and slide sharing. It makes the lecturer more comfortable with the system and is an opportunity to discuss last minute issues. It is a good idea to go through the structure of the seminar once more.

- We did not use the video feature but **having the lecturer`s photo on the start slide** can be a good idea.
- **Involve a second person** to make a backup recording of the seminar and co-moderate or help with technical aspects during the online seminars. This does not only help with the technical running of the session but having another speak regularly encourages participants to become more active in a digital learning environment.
- Make a very short (max 5 minutes) **feedback survey after each session** asking participants to reflect on course content, design and pedagogy. Send the link and give students time to complete the digital evaluation during or right at the end of the seminar. Have an open comments box. Show how you have incorporated past feedback into your coming seminars.
- **Course feedback survey:** Encourage students to complete the evaluation by discussing its purpose and importance in the weeks leading up to it. If students know that their feedback will influence how future similar events are made, they will be more likely to complete the evaluation. **Much of these “lessons learned” comes from these feedback surveys**, and especially open question formats that allow the participants to share their individual perspective and practical tips about new online platforms, for example.

After the course

- Send lecturers the link to the recordings.
- Upload all material (videos, case studies) and update links on the course webpage.
- Send out the course certificate.

Content:

Seminars:

A **seminar structure** that works well for 1.5 hours:

- Introduction: At the beginning of your seminar, the moderator uses about 5 minutes for seminar logistics to explain key functions in Zoom and to introduce the speaker.
- First part talk: We recommend starting the lecture with an about 10 minutes long introduction to the topic, this can be rather a general overview.
- Quiz: Next, we suggest taking 5 minutes for a quiz in Mentimeter or Kahoot, or a Zoom Poll, to make sure students are all on the same page and that the basic direction of the lecture topic is understood. If there is something that turns out to be unclear, it can be re-explained immediately.
- 2nd part talk: After this, we recommend spending no more than 20-25 minutes on the specific topic or examples. For example, this can be a conference talk that you may have already prepared.
- Q&A: Reserve about ½ hour after the lecture and discussions. Book the Zoom system for long enough so there is a time buffer.

Online Group Work:

- Organize an **initial online meeting** with each group individually to introduce the group members, take a closer look at the provided guidelines, templates and examples and discuss the time schedule, expectations and questions. This meeting could also be used to discuss how to define the topic/direction of the case study and how to set up future communication and meetings. Addressing these points and finding a group leader in an online meeting rather than via email serves an “icebreaker” that would give each group a better dynamic from the start.
- Regular check-ins and short status updates (1-2 sentences) via a form in google docs to be updated by the group leader were a good way to follow up on the progress of each group, get in touch when difficulties arise, or find out the timeline needs to be adjusted.

- Provide **suggestions for communication tools** to the groups at the beginning, e.g. WhatsApp, GoogleHangouts, Skype or Zoom. Different communication platforms such as Piazza or Blackboard could also be explored more. The course organiser was also part of the group mailing lists so that discussed content could be followed, and the course organiser could step in in case of more serious issues.
- **Involving a mentor** from among the APPLICATE researcher or stakeholder community who could help the groups e.g. with finding and contacting stakeholders. This was difficult in the setup phase as the case studies were more generally formulated to encourage the students to choose their own topics. This means possible mentors had to be contacted on a too short notice about their potential involvement.
- For this course, the groups were set up based on similar background and interest. Another way to facilitate better communication would be **dividing the groups based on location/time zone** to avoid a large spread in time zones that may lead to slow communication and difficulties to find suitable time slots for online meetings.
- With the circumstances of an online course with participants with limited background and time schedule, it may be acceptable to **limit the choice to better predefined topics** for the next time. This would also allow better to involve mentors that can help improve the case study through specific feedback, and possibly lead to a continuation of the work after the course towards e.g. in the form of a publication.
- Expose participants to a **peer review process** (e.g. review the work of another group). This is a skill that rarely gets practiced in everyday teaching but learning how to give constructive feedback is a skill that certainly adds value to the course. To ensure a positive outcome, clear guidelines about expectations of the report and how to give the feedback were provided. Since the peer review was carried out in a larger group, the risk of inappropriate feedback from a single person was greatly reduced. The peer review went smoothly with all groups providing their input on time, written in a critical but positive tone, in a well-structured order and with constructive content. All groups considerably improved their case study after the peer review round.

3. Collection of Polar Prediction Resources

Throughout the lifetime of the APPLICATE project, we have collected a number of [resources on the topic of polar prediction](#) that are available on the APECS website. These resources include:

- Specific online resources, materials and tutorials related to Polar prediction,
- Online learning platforms that offer more general courses of relevance to Polar predictions,
- And further interesting resources.

Link to the resources: <https://apecs.is/research/apecs-projects/applicate/384-polar-prediction-resources.html>

4. Conclusion

Comprehensive and targeted in-person and online training activities accompanied the APPLICATE project that addressed a wide variety of topics and skills. They represent valuable online resources and a legacy of the APPLICATE and YOPP projects. The activities and events were successful with a wealth of lessons learned and summarized in this document.

The early career polar researcher community shows strong interest and commitment in training opportunities both in-person and online that APECS caters for example through its

involvement in the APPLICATE project, but also through the invaluable work of its dedicated members.

5. Annexes

5.1 Polar Prediction School 2018: List of instructors, students, organising committee, sponsors

Instructors

- **Ian Brooks** (University of Leeds, United Kingdom)
- **Matthieu Chevallier** (Meteo France, France)
- **Jonathan Day** (ECMWF, United Kingdom)
- **Anna Fitch** (Stockholm University, Sweden)
- **Martin Hagman** (Stockholm University / Swedish Armed Forces, Sweden)
- **Anna Hogg** (University of Leeds, United Kingdom)
- **Thomas Jung** (Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI), Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Germany)
- **Erik Kolstad** (Bjerknes Centre for Climate Research / University of Bergen, Norway)
- **Linus Magnusson** (ECMWF, United Kingdom)
- **Donald Perovich** (Dartmouth College, United States)
- **Jessica Rodhe** (Interagency Arctic Research Policy Committee (IARPC), United States)
- **Doug Smith** (Met Office Hadley Centre for Climate Science and Services, United Kingdom)
- **Gunilla Svensson** (Stockholm University, Sweden)

Participants:

- **Helene Asbjørnsen** (PhD candidate, University of Bergen, Norway)
- **Chris Barrel** (PhD candidate, University of East Anglia, United Kingdom)
- **Benjamin Barton** (PhD candidate, Bangor University, UK and LOPS in Brest, France)
- **Yurii Batrak** (Researcher, Norwegian Meteorological Institute in Oslo, Norway)
- **Clara Burgard** (PhD candidate, Max Planck Institute for Meteorology, Germany)
- **Fernanda Casagrande** (Meteorologist, Federal University of Pelotas, Brazil)
- **Sam Cornish** (PhD candidate, University of Oxford, United Kingdom)
- **Ying Dai** (Postdoc, Max-Planck-Institute for Meteorology, Germany)
- **Evelien Dekker** (PhD candidate, Stockholm University, Sweden)
- **Rebecca Frew** (PhD candidate, University of Reading, United Kingdom)
- **Ella Gilbert** (PhD candidate, British Antarctic Survey and University of Cambridge, United Kingdom)
- **Martin Hagman** (PhD candidate, Stockholm University, Sweden, and forecaster in the Swedish Armed Forces)
- **Kasper Hintz** (PhD candidate, Danish Meteorological Institute, Denmark)

- **Stefan Kowalewski** (Postdoc, AWI, Germany)
- **Flo Lemonnier** (PhD candidate, Sorbonne University in Paris, France)
- **Alexander Lohse** (Postdoc, University of Hamburg, Germany)
- **Mallik Mahmud** (PhD candidate, University of Calgary, Canada)
- **Christine McKenna** (PhD candidate, British Antarctic Survey and University of Cambridge, United Kingdom)
- **Pia Nielsen** (Researcher, Danish Meteorological Institute, Denmark)
- **Jan Nitzbon** (PhD candidate, AWI, Germany)
- **Leandro Ponsoni** (Researcher, Université Catholique de Louvain, Belgium)
- **Kabir Rasouli** (Postdoc, University of Calgary, Canada)
- **Patrick Stoll** (PhD candidate, UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Norway)
- **Jenny Turton** (Postdoc, University of Erlangen-Nuremberg, Germany)
- **Alexander Vessey** (PhD candidate, University of Reading, United Kingdom)
- **James Warner** (PhD candidate, NASA, United States)
- **Sally Woodhouse** (PhD candidate, University of Reading, United Kingdom)
- **Cheng You** (PhD candidate, Stockholm University, Sweden)
- **Lorenzo Zampieri** (PhD candidate, AWI, Germany)

Organising committee:

- **Fiona Tummon** (APECS Directorate Office/UiT The Arctic University of Norway, Norway)
- **Alice Bradley** (Dartmouth College, United States)
- **Ian Brooks** (University of Leeds, United Kingdom)
- **Luisa Cristini** (Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI), Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Germany)
- **Jonathan Day** (University of Reading, United Kingdom)
- **Gerlis Fugmann** (APECS Directorate Office/Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Germany)
- **Thomas Jung** (Alfred Wegener Institut for Polar and Marine Research, Germany)
- **Gunilla Svensson** (Stockholm University, Sweden)
- **Kirstin Werner** (Alfred Wegener Institut for Polar and Marine Research, Germany)

5.2 Polar Prediction School 2018 survey graphs

Explanation: Answers ranged from 1 (not at all) to 10 (yes definitely).

Did the course curriculum meet your expectations?

27 responses

Did you think the lectures covered a good range of topics?

27 responses

Did you find the lecture content appropriate?

27 responses

Were the science communication sessions relevant and useful?

27 responses

Were the lectures logically ordered?

27 responses

Was the mix of lectures, practicals, and exercises well structured?

27 responses

Was there sufficient time allocated to the different lectures?

27 responses

Was there sufficient time allocated to the practicals?

27 responses

5.3 APPLICATE Online Course 2019: List of instructors and organising committee

Instructors and affiliation:

- **Thomas Jung** (Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar and Marine Research, Germany)
- **Marta Terrado** (Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Spain)
- **Dragana Bojovic** (Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Spain)
- **Gunilla Svensson** (Stockholm University, Sweden)
- **Taneil Uttal** (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, United States)
- **Heather Lawrence** (European Center For Medium Range Weather Forecasts, United Kingdom)
- **Doug Smith** (MetOffice, United Kingdom)
- **Thomas Spengler** (University of Bergen, Norway)
- **Arlan Dirkson** (Université du Québec à Montréal, Canada)
- **Irina Sandu** (European Center For Medium Range Weather Forecasts, United Kingdom)
- **Barbara Casati** (Environmental and Climate Change Canada, Canada)
- **Jonny Day** (European Center For Medium Range Weather Forecasts, United Kingdom)

Organising committee and affiliation:

- **Andrea Schneider**, Course Administrator (Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) / UiT The Arctic University of Norway)
- **Natalie Carter** (University of Ottawa, Canada)
- **Luisa Cristini** (APPLICATE / Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Germany)
- **Gerlis Fugmann** (Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS)/ Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Germany)
- **Deniz Vural** (Istanbul Technical University Polar Research Center)
- **Paul Rosenbaum** (Uppsala University, Sweden)
- **Fiona Tummon** (Federal Office of Meteorology and Climatology MeteoSwiss, Switzerland)
- **Kirstin Werner** (International Coordination Office for Polar Prediction (ICO)/Alfred Wegener Institute, Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research, Germany)

5.4 APPLICATE Online Course 2019 survey graphs

The course curriculum met my expectations.

40 responses

The course gave me a deeper insight and understanding in Polar weather and climate predictions.

40 responses

There was sufficient time allocated to the curriculum subjects.

40 responses

The combination of lectures and practical work was structured well.

40 responses

The course organisers provided guidance and feedback.

40 responses

My group communicated and worked efficiently.

40 responses

The practical work on the case studies added value to the course.

40 responses

Considering both the limitations and possibilities of the subject matter and the course, how would you rate the overall effectiveness of this course?

40 responses

The course developed my abilities and skills for ...

40 responses

On average, how many hours per week have you spent on this course (including attending webinars, reading, reviewing notes, working on the case studies, and any other course-related work)?
40 responses

5.5 APPLICATE Online Course 2019 Certificate

Certificate of Completion

(Name of the student)

successfully completed the
**APECS-APPLICATE-YOPP Online course 2019 on
"Advancing Predictive Capability of Northern Hemisphere Weather and
Climate"**
with a case study about

(Title of the case study)

The course was run between September 19 and December 05, 2019, and included 12 interactive seminars, developing and presenting a compulsory case study, and voluntary reading.

A lecture plan can be found on page two of this certificate and additional details about the course, the speakers and the case study can be found on the course website:

<https://www.apecs.is/research/apecs-projects/applicate/applicate-online-course-2019.html>.

Dr. Andrea Schneider
(Course administrator)

Dr. Gerlis Fugmann
(APECS Executive Director)

APECS-APPLICATE-YOPP Online course 2019 Lecture plan
"Advancing Predictive Capability of Northern Hemisphere Weather and Climate"

Date	Title	Presenter	Duration (min)
Block 1: Introduction			
19 Sept	Course introduction: Advancing Predictive Capability of Northern Hemisphere Weather and Climate	Thomas Jung (Alfred Wegener Institute for Polar & Marine Research, Germany)	90
26 Sept	Stakeholder engagement and examples of APPLICATE case studies	Marta Terrado & Dragana Bojovic (Barcelona Supercomputing Center, Spain)	70
03 Oct	Boundary layer, clouds and air mass transformation	Gunilla Svensson (Stockholm University, Sweden)	70
Block 2 - Data and modelling			
17 Oct	Observing system design in the Arctic	Taneil Uttal (National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, United States)	80
24 Oct	The use of Arctic observations in Numerical Weather Prediction	Heather Lawrence (European Center For Medium Range Weather Forecasts, UK)	50
31 Oct	Seasonal to decadal prediction: recent progress & signal-to-noise paradox	Doug Smith (MetOffice, United Kingdom)	80
07 Nov	Arctic weather phenomena and extremes	Thomas Spengler (University of Bergen, Norway)	90
Block 3 - Arctic			
14 Nov	Polar ocean forecasting	Arlan Dirkson (Université du Québec à Montréal, Canada)	90
21 Nov	Challenges and priorities for improved prediction and climate monitoring of the Arctic	Irina Sandu (European Center For Medium Range Weather Forecasts, UK)	70
28 Nov	Evaluating models	Barbara Casati (Environmental and Climate Change Canada)	90
04 Dec	Case study presentation seminar	Course participants	90
05 Dec	APPLICATE and the Year Of Polar Prediction (YOPP)	Jonathan Day (European Center For Medium Range Weather Forecasts, UK)	60